

Corporate Governance And Value Of Banks Providing Internet Banking In The 4.0 Industry Era (A Meta Research)

Moeljadi, Yusuf Iskandar, Susenohaji

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 06, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: October 06, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Interest Rate, Firm Value, Liquidity, Profitability Bank, Overhead Bank, Corporate Governance</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5553297</p>	<p><i>Objective: The purpose of this research is to explore corporate governance, inter-est rate, liquidity, firm value, overhead, profitability, bank efficiency, and bank value in emerging digitalization market trends.</i></p> <p><i>Methodology/Technique: This study was used meta analysis to illustrate some differences between a results of studies. It must have obtain an existing research by provide an explanation of the different things about variables.</i></p> <p><i>Findings: A research model has been carried out in the banking industry, and has been carried out with a well-established research model, such the "firm size" and capital structure. This study also wants to see the elements of "bank efficiency" and "interest rates". The results of the research also complement other international journal articles, in order to complement the material used in the dissertation. Novelty: In this research also proved that it can affect to Firm Value in the Indus-trial Era 4.0. Good governance is a condition of managing a bank by meeting the guidelines for good bank management, which was expected by investors.</i></p>

Introduction

The implementation of Good Corporate Governance (GCG) in the Bank in the era of digitalization has an influence on the value of the company. Good Corporate Governance plays an important role in the Bank's operations in achieving financial results. Good Corporate Governance is required by Bank institutions in their operations in any period of time and period, and supervision is also for supervision by the OJK. In the current digital era, it has changed the management chain of all industries including the financial / banking industry, with digital financial technology and banking equipment (Setiawan, 2019). This is by banks in order to maximize their business. Information technology includes additional equipment, software, firmware, procedures, and services. With information technology, it is able to process large amounts of transactions, thus making banks more efficient (Dangolani, 2011). The development of digital technology in this new era has also created problems for banks that are not ready to fund investments in digital infrastructure. The current era of digitalization will definitely improve bank financial performance, and its impact will increase share prices. In this case, the level of bank profitability is very important in generating financial performance.

On the other hand, a small size of the bank company, in general the number of assets owned by a bank can affect the costs incurred in the current digital era. Decisions taken, for example, whether the bank needs to invest itself or lease the assets used. For the larger asset ownership has a greater ability to collaborate with Financial technology institutions. Then, a bigger the ownership of bank assets can attract customers to save. In asset management, it is not only assets that are managed physically, but also assets that are intangible in nature. Any decision to invest or not to invest is determined by the bank and the supervisory committee in the bank. Good governance can achieve good performance including transparency, accountability, and responsibility.

An existence of concentrated ownership can improve leverage (Lazarides, 2019), because concentrated with ownership can increase supervision / control, which will increase accountability and increase company value. Firm value can determine the level of good bank management and good bank operationalization. Good bank management can also increase profitability, because profitability can guarantee bank operations. Bank operational costs, among others, are contributed by bank operating income, which plays an important role in bank operations. The main assessment of the bank as measured by profitability over time (Bikker and Bos, 2005). Banks apply profits to shareholders through returns on investment in bank shares in the form of capital gains for bank shares and through dividends (Bikker and Bos, 2008). The maximization of investment returns can be achieved by means of good governance. Profitability is related to internal factors, including an ability to minimize risk, operational efficiency, and bank size (Fisseha, 2015).

A bank takes anticipatory action through better management (good governance) and collaborates with information technology companies to provide digital systems in order to keep the market from experiencing a rush, for example Amarthabank which functions in Peer to Peer Lending funded by Mandiri Bank (Afriyadi, 2017).

Profitability for banks were go public is not like final goal, because shareholders have standards in achieving profitability. A reflection of the level of satisfaction of shareholders with the achievement of bank profitability can be seen in Bank Value. Regarding a price that investors are willing to pay in relation to the stock price through a high level of profitability. A higher the stock price on the capital market, also can higher the appreciation of investors, which was reflected in the higher the value of profitability. A high company value illustrated that the bank's financial performance is in good condition, so that it can convince investors of the good and bad of the bank in the future (Bell and Filatotchev, 2014).

Various an empirical studies as the capital structure is a significant impact on firm value (Modigliani and Miller, 1963), because the proportion of funding that comes from loans or customer funds will affect their profitability. Although Kodongo and Mokoteli, (2014) founded that the capital structure of companies listed on the Kenyan stock exchange has no effect on Firm Value. The results have been add to the analysis in the required meta analysis. As will prove or analyze the capital structure affects to the stock price offer (Alti, 2006; Masulis, 1983).

Some problems such as good governance and firm value can be analyzed by conducting meta analysis, with a research analysis model that can be used to easily determined by the problem about conceptual framework. It would be related to the development of Good Corporate Governance. Furthermore, this meta analysis and meta research model / program can be developed in the bank / other.

TEORITICAL FRAMEWORK

Bank Profitability

Many kinds of factors can affecting to bank profitability, which are divided about internal and external, and this applies whether the bank in question forms part of a domestic study or an international study, as in this case. Many of the internal determinants reviewed in the literature rely for their estimation on data which are available in limited, local, typically (Haslam, 1968).

Firm Value

Firm Value also described with a measure of the actual economic value of a company at any given moment. Firm Value expresses what is the fair price to buy all bank assets. Firm Value is a reflection of a bank's investment, financial and dividend decisions (Rajhans & Kaur, 2013). Investors use the company value of all outstanding shares firm value. This approach is known as market capitalization or the market value of all shares, which is equal to the number of shares outstanding, so measurement is related to the stock price at present. If there is a change in the composition of a bank's capital structure, for example, there is additional capital from retained earnings, it can increase its market value (Chowdhury & Chowdhury, 2010). Banks are able to minimize costs and then capital costs can maximize firm value.

Corporate Governance

Corporate governance according to the Turnbull Report in England (April 1999) quoted by Tsuguoki Fujinuma is: "Corporate governance is the company's system if internal control has as its principal aim the management of risk that is significant to the fulfillment of its business objectives with a view to safeguarding the company's assets and enhancing overtime the value of the shareholders Investment ". Based on the above definition, corporate governance as a company internal control system with the main objective of managing significant risks in order to fulfill its business objectives through safeguarding company assets and increasing likely investment value for shareholders in the long term (Effendi, 2016; 2).

According to the World Bank (World Bank), the definition of good corporate governance (GCG) is a collection of laws, regulations and rules that must be fulfilled that can encourage the performance of company resources to function efficiently in order to produce long-term sustainable economic value for the holders. Shares and the surrounding community as a whole. The notion of governance can be interpreted as a way of managing public affairs. The notion of good governance is often defined as good governance (governance). The World Bank provides a definition of governance as: "the way state power is used in managing economic and social resources for development of society".

The World Bank defines good governance as an implementation of solid and responsible development management in line with the principles of democracy and an efficient market, avoiding misallocation of investment funds, and preventing corruption, both politically and administratively, implementing budget discipline and creating a legal and political framework for the growth of business activities.

Implementation of Good Corporate Governance in Bank

There are 2 (two) balanced views in determining whether or not a Good Corporate Governance implementation guideline is needed in a company (Abor and Adjasi, 2007). First, the view that explains the need for Good Corporate Governance in bank. Agency problems occur because of the two interests of the owner and manager. The second view is that there is global attention to the implementation of Good Corporate Governance (GCG). Guidelines for publicly listed companies (go public) should consider these aspects complexity, but on the application of the principles for implementing an effective system of governance.

The benefit of implementing good corporate governance in the company is that they are entrepreneurs who grow and the company will become a big business (Big Business). Every company needs additional resources and funds (such as: finance, assets, and technology) to grow, the application of Good Corporate Governance principles will increase its bankable status. Investable, and firm value in the company.

Based on researcher by Moeljadi, et al. (2020) was discussed that NIM and EOTA had a direct effect on Firm Value (stock prices), but did not affect FV (stock returns). Loan Deposit Ration (LDR) has no effect on Firm Value (stock prices and stock returns). Return On Asset (ROA) is proven to mediate the influence of NIM on Firm Value (share price). Banks must pay attention to factors both internal and external to increase investor confidence as reflected in stock prices. However, the increase in share prices that is not balanced with an increase in stock returns needs attention from banks and investors.

METHODOLOGY

This study was used by a qualitative approach with meta research that existing research (Marsano, 1998, p. 5). Meta research also illustrated by the differences between a results of existing studies. This means that researchers must obtain an existing research result by providing an explanation for each other research, differently.

In one study, the company size has a significant effect on firm value. Other studies on the same say different results, so those differences need "explanation". This explanation is a finding or discussion in Meta Research or Meta Analysis.

This research study was examined by research experts using multiple research paradigms, which is rarely conducted. In quite contrast, research methods are used by quantitative results and qualitative results.

This study has a method that used by meta-analysis with reference to secondary data from the results including quantitative research coupled for special analysis from other research. Thus, a data was collected in the form on interview and secondary data such as literature studies and taking data from existing research results (stock taking), then a data has been processed descriptively and analytically.

The analysis was used by secondary data with qualitative methods. Every data collected and the results of other studies that have been conducted are analyzed. This analysis is intended to understand the "full" conclusion of good governance exists and obtain reliable results. As stated by Lock, et al., (1987) and John W. Creswell (2002) assumed that the research method must give many more researcher a role to provide something useful.

RESULTS

The Banking Industry is an industry that is very important in the Indonesian economy in the current Industry 4.0. The intermediary banking function is an important part in developing the real sector. In encouraging development, banks will channel credit for distribution in the community. This important role is that each bank must be able to manage its business well, in order to gain the trust of stakeholders.

In this quite contrast, Good Corporate Governance have been carried out by companies in various countries and for large companies listed on stock exchanges (OECD, 2006). There are who stated that Good Corporate Governance is important and some those who said is not important. Good Corporate Governance still has challenges to be implemented in companies, especially bank buku 1 (bank with small operational system), and especially in emerging countries. However, any development of digitalization in the current era, it seems that small companies must be able to work well, because the community's need for small industrial products is very much needed. Additionally, researcher on the topic of corporate governance in banking still needed, although

even the OECD has also published a book on "corporate governance of non-listed companies in emerging markets".

The Implementation of Corporate Governance in Bank

The good governance system mechanism has been implemented with large bank (buku III and IV), which is requires a lot of adjustments to the organizational structure and quite complex, then expensive, absolutely.

The most of the Bank's companies are still running their business conventionally and have not implemented the principles of good corporate governance. However, the guidelines and regulations regarding the implementation of good corporate governance are more appropriate in large-scale bank, where the tendency is to become too heavy for the implementation of the Bank's companies. This condition encourages some government, banks, and academics to identify problems and find solutions for how to implement a good corporate governance in this potential banking sector. Good Corporate Governance is believed to be able to improve the quality of Bank management and ultimately increase the trust of stakeholders. The implementation of good corporate governance is useful in helping banks improve their prospects in order to obtain alternative funding from both investors and financial institutions. In practice, business principles also applied by a bank can be linked to the concept of governance, which is applied to the types of large businesses today.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

The results were indicated that matters related to the concept and model of research carried out in banking. It is needs to develop meta research models in other fields. The approach taken is a qualitative approach by providing a full explanation (positivist). The results were reinforced that the relationship between variables in the study is more meaningful, because it is not only seen from one perspective, but also by using a broader perspective. The research takes a Good Corporate Governance that suitable in the important things for manage many bank and also assumed with investment, which are probably responses to another bank with a good professional managers such as strategic in the digital financial industry.

SUGGESTION

The suggestion for this paper that I can merely a meta analysis can provide an overview of the customer's position in determining deposit rates, reducing information asymmetry, and agency conflicts in determining interest rates.

REFERENCES

- Abbasi, T., & Weigand, H. (2017). The Impact of Digital Financial Services on Firm's Performance Literature Review. Department of Management Tilburg School of Economics and Management Tilburg University, The Netherlands, pages 1-15.
- Abel, A. B., Bernanke, B. S., & Croushore, D. (2008). *Macroeconomic*. Boston: Pearson Education, Inc. .
- Abid, F., & Lodhi, S. (2015). Impact of Changes in Reserve Requirement on Banks Profitability: A Case of Commercial Banks in Pakistan. *European Journal of Business and Management*, pages 1-6.
- Adelopo, I., Lloydking, R., & Tauringana, V. (2018). Determinants of Bank Profitability Before, During, and After The Financial Crisis. *International Journal of Managerial Finance*.
- Adjei-Frimpong, K., Gan, C., & Hu, B. (2014). Cost Efficiency of Ghana's Banking Industry: A Panel Data Analysis. *The International Journal of Business and Finance Research*, pages 69-86.
- Ajanthan, A. (2013). Impact of Corporate Governance Practices on Firm Capital Structure and Profitability: A Study of Selected Hotels and Restaurant Companies in Sri Lanka. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 4(10), 115-124. doi: <http://www.iiste.org/Journals/index.php/RJFA/article/view/7155>
- Albulescu, C. T. (2015). Banks' Profitability and Financial Soundness Indicators: A Macro Level Investigation in Emerging Countries. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, pages 203-209 .
- Al-Kayed, Lama Tarek, Zain, Sharifah Raihan Syed Mohd, dan Duasa, Jarita. (2014). The relationship between capital structure and performance of Islamic banks. *Journal of Islamic Accounting and Business Research*, 5(2), 158-181. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/JIABR-04-2012-0024>
- Almazari, A. A. (2014). Impact of Internal Factors on Bank Profitability: Comparative Study between Saudi Arabia and Jordan. *Journal of Applied Finance & Banking*, pages 125-140.
- AL-Omar, Husain, dan AL-Mutairi, Abdullah. (2008). Bank-Specific Determinants of Profitability: The case of Kuwait. *Journal of Economic & Administrative Sciences* 24(2). doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/10264116200800006>
- Ardela, F. (2017, Oktober 24). Teknologi Finansial: Tengok Dulu Perkembangan Fintech Di Indonesia! Retrieved April 22, 2018, from *Finansialku.com*: <https://www.finansialku.com>
- Argacia, J. (2019). Review Jurnal The Development of Digital Economy in Indonesia - Josephine Argacia. preprint. doi:DOI: 10.31227/osf.io/xftkb
- Bank Indonesia. (2017). Peraturan Bank Indonesia Nomor 19/14/PADG/2017 tentang Ruang Uji Coba Terbatas (Regulatory Sandbox) Teknologi Finansial.
- Bank Indonesia. (2017). Peraturan Bank Indonesia Nomor 19/15/PADG/2017 tentang Tata Cara Pendaftaran, Penyampaian Informasi, dan Pemantauan Penyelenggara Teknologi Finansial .
- Basel Committee on Banking Supervision. (2018). Implications of Fintech Developments for Banks and Bank Supervisors. online: Bank for International Settlements.
- Bikker, J. A., & Boss, J. W. (2008). *Bank Performance: A theoretical and Empirical Framework for The analysis of Profitability, Competition and Efficiency*. Netherlands: Taylor & Francis Group, LLC.
- Bikker, J. A., & Elgar, E. (2004). *Competition and Efficiency in a Unified European Banking Market*. London: Edward Elgar Publishing Limited.
- Brigham, Eugene F., dan Daves, Phillip R. (2011). *Intermediate Financial Management*. United States: Thomson Higher Education.
- Cavus, N., & Chingoka, D. N. (2015). Information Technology in The Banking Sector: Review of Mobile Banking. *Global Journal of Information Technology*, volume 5, issue (2), pages 62-70.
- Chaudhry, M., Chatrath, A., & Kamath, R. (2015). Determinants of Bank Profitability. *American Journal of Business*, pages 41-46.
- Chaudhry, Mukesh, Chatrath, Arjun, dan Kamath, Ravindra. (1995). Determinants of Bank Profitability. *American Journal of Business Research*, 10(1), 41-46. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1108/19355181199500005>
- Chauvin, K. W., & Hirshey, M. (1994). Goodwill, Profitability, Market Value of the Firm. *Journal of Accounting and Public Policy*, pages 159-180.
- Dahmash, F. N. (2015). Size Effect on Company Profitability: Evidence from Jordan. *International Journal of Business and Management*, pages 58-72.
- Dahmash, Firas Naim. (2015). Size Effect on Company Profitability: Evidence from Jordan. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 10(2), 58-72. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5539/ijbm.v10n2p58>
- Dimand, Robert W. (2008). "Macroeconomics, origins and history of". In Durlauf, Steven N.; Blume, Lawrence E. (eds.). *The New Palgrave Dictionary of Economics*. The New Palgrave Dictionary of Economics. Palgrave Macmillan. doi:10.1057/9780230226203.1009. ISBN 978-0-333-78676-5.
- Eltabakh, M. L., Ngamkroekjoti, C., & Ismail Ali Siad. (2014). A comparison Study on The Profitability and its Determinants between Islamic and Conventional Banks Listed in Qatar Exchange (QE) Pre, During, and Post 2008 Global Financial Crisis. *International Conference on Business, Law and Corporate Social Responsibility* (pp. 91-95). Phuket Thailand: International Conference on Business, Law and Corporate Social Responsibility.

- Garcia, M. T., & Guerreiro, J. P. (2016). Internal and external determinants of banks' profitability: The Portuguese case. *Journal of Economic Studies*, pages 90-107.
- Gauti B. Eggertsson (2008). "liquidity trap," *The New Palgrave Dictionary of Economics*, 2nd Edition.
- Gibson, J. (2015). *The Impact FinTech is having on the Financial Services Industry in Ireland*. Dublin: Dublin Business School.
- Haron, S. (2004). Determinants of Islamic Bank Profitability. *Global Journal of Finance and Economics USA*.
- Ismail, A. G., Karim, Z. A., & Wahid, H. (2006). Interest Rate Uncertainty Spread and Economic Activity: Empirical Evidence in Malaysia. *Jurnal Ekonomi Pembangunan*, pages 187-199.
- Kioko, N. P. (2013). *The Relationship Between Firm Size and Financial Performance of Commercial Banks in Kenya*. Nairobi: University of Nairobi.
- Koch, T. W., & MacDonald, S. S. (2015). *Bank Management*. Boston: Cengage Learning.
- Kodongo, O., Mokoteli, T. M., & Maina, L. (2014). Capital Structure, Profitability and Firm Value: Panel Evidence of Listed Firms in Kenya. *Munich Personal RePEc Archive (MPRA)*, pages 1-19.
- Lensink, R., & Hermes, N. (2004). The Short-term Effects of Foreign Bank Entry on Domestic Bank Behaviour: Does Economic Development Matter?. *Journal of Banking & Finance*, pages 553-568.
- Marozva, G. (2015). Liquidity And Bank Performance. *International Business & Economics Research Journal*, pages 453-461.
- Marsano, Robert J, 1998, *Theory bas Meta Analysis*, McREL Publication, Colorado
- Menicucci, E., & Paolucci, G. (2016). The Determinants of Bank Profitability: Empirical Evidence from European Banking Sector. *Journal of Financial Reporting and Accounting*, pages 86-115.
- Mitra, G., & Schwaiger, K. (2011). *Asset and Liability Management Handbook*. London: PalgraveMacmillan.
- Moeljadi, Titisari, K.H., Supriyati, T.S., and Yuniarsa, S.O. (2020). Determinant Firm Value Of The Banking Sector Listing On The Indonesia Stock Exchange: Mediated By Profitability. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SCIENTIFIC & TECHNOLOGY RESEARCH*, VOLUME 9, ISSUE 04
- Panico, Carlo (2008). "liquidity preference". In Durlauf, Steven N.; Blume, Lawrence E. (eds.). *The New Palgrave Dictionary of Economics*. Palgrave Macmillan.
- Petria, N., Caprarub, B., & Ihnatovc, I. (2015). Determinants of Banks' Profitability: Evidence from EU 27 Banking Systems. *Elsevier*, pages 518-524.
- Siddik, Md. Nur Alam, Kabiraj, Sajal, dan Joghee, Shanmugan. (2017). Impacts of Capital Structure on Performance of Banks in a Developing Economy: Evidence from Bangladesh. *International Journal of Financial Studies*, 5(13). doi: <http://ideas.repec.org/a/gam/jjifss/v5y2017i2p13-d97401.html>
- Sucuaahi, W., & Cambarihan, J. M. (2016). Influence of Profitability to the Firm Value of Diversified Companies in the Philippines. www.sciedupress.com, pages 149-153.
- Sufian, F. (2009). Determinants of Bank Profitability in a Developing Economy: Empirical Evidence from the China Banking Sector. *Journal of Asia-Pacific Business*, pages 281-3017.
- Zhang, C., & Dong, L. (2011). *Determinants of Bank Profitability: Evidence from The U.S Banking Sector*. Burnaby: Simon Fraser University.

Author Information

Moeljadi

Professor of Management Department, Faculty of Economics and Business, Universitas Brawijaya, Malang, Indonesia

Yusuf Iskandar

Doctorate Student of Management Department, Faculty of Economics and Business, University of Brawijaya, Malang, Indonesia

Susenoahaji

Doctorate Student of Management Department, Faculty of Economics and Business, University of Brawijaya, Malang, Indonesia
